

Ethical Debt, Underworld Officials, and Embodied Effort in the Love of Mortals in the Final Chapter of Curious Tales of a Temple

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Abstract

This review analyzes the final chapter of *Curious Tales of a Temple*, examining how karmic justice, ethical debts, and resurrection structure the film's moral universe and could provide insights for romantic relationship. Zhang Sheng's embodied acts of devotion not only repay Luying's ethical debts of last life, but also redirect her destiny, positively functioning as a moralization of the deeply rooted Chinese ethic that obligations to the past and to the deceased must be honored. The portrayal of underworld figures such as Meng Po and the Black and White impermanence reinforces this order. Monumental in scale and awe-inspiring in presence, they embody the impersonal machinery of karmic law, teaching moral lessons while withholding personal intervention. Finally, set against the myth of Orpheus, Zhang Sheng's refusal to turn back emphasizes action over retrospection and anchors love in ceaseless labor. Love itself is thus reconfigured as a cycle of reciprocity and indebtedness, where salvation and renewal arise through perseverance, care, and ceaseless embodied effort.

Keywords: Curious Tales of a Temple; debts; karmic ties; underworld officials; reciprocity; embodied effort

1. Introduction

The final chapter of *Curious Tales of a Temple* presents one of the most insightful reimagination of classical ghost-romance narratives. Far from being a simple continuation of its literary source, the film reshapes the story into a meditation on ethical laws, figures of underworld officials, and love's endurance across mortal boundaries. This paper examines the deep folk meanings and explores how its depiction of love becomes both culturally grounded and philosophically suggestive. The first two sections mainly focus on the film's establishment of its ethical universe by analyzing its plot. The film is rich in its folk resonances, especially how karmic debt, resurrection, divine intervention, and underworld officials represent familiar mythological motifs in innovative ways. The third section dives into a cross-cultural comparison with the myth of Orpheus. Both narratives center on lovers confronting the underworld, yet the Chinese film diverges significantly from the Greek myth. The fourth section further suggests how this difference may offer new insights into romantic relationships. The film ultimately articulates a vision of love as reciprocal and embodied, enacted not in symbolic retrospection but in the lived materiality of ceaseless devotion.

2. The Repay of Ethical Debts

Examining the film's deviations from the original text allows us to understand how *Curious Tales of a Temple* constructs its ethical universe. The final chapter of the film *Curious Tales of a Temple* departs most strikingly from its

original text by removing the scene where Zhang Sheng is invited in a dream by immortals to drink tea, bathe, cleanse himself of mortal impurity, and regain youth. To maintain coherence with the subsequent events of the original, the film introduces another figure, namely Meng Po, to enable Zhang Sheng's rejuvenation. Here, Meng Po promises him that when he faces difficulties, he may return to the well at Lanruo Temple, where she will grant him a chance, bestowing upon him a divine elixir of youth. Though this divine intervention is separated by fifteen years later from Luying's reincarnation, when she makes the vow to continue their love in another life, cinematic editing of montage compresses this interval. Symbolically, Zhang Sheng thus becomes bound by two karmic ties: one, a vow of human love, the unresolved bond with Luying; the other, a divine gift, heaven's compassion for their separation by life and death. These dual obligations form the entry point for understanding the logic of debt that structures the film's ethical universe.

In the film, death does not carry Luying directly into the cycle of rebirth, where every soul is judged by its sins and virtues. The film grants her a pause, a rare exception, so that she can make up for her sins. This motif of "resurrect to atone for sins" derives from traditional Chinese conceptions of death, which hold that one's earthly actions will be accounted for after passing. As Ding and Zhang (2023) explain, the "ethics of debt-responsibility" in Chinese society transcend economic relations, evolving into a broader moral system encompassing "historical ethics" and "memory ethics." The logic of indebtedness extends beyond material obligations into karmic and emotional domains, binding past lives, the present, and future reincarnations into a continuous chain. Zhang Sheng's act of atoning on behalf of Luying reflects the notions that the living bears a sense of indebtedness to the deceased and that obligations to the past must be fulfilled through actions. Luying's sins are offset, as the unresolved debts of her former existence are fulfilled. This process of redemption embodies the conviction that debts, whether ethical or material, must be repaid. It is a central tenet of traditional Chinese understandings of the law of cause and effect.

The question is, however, why is Luying specifically granted such a rare chance to repay her debts? The answer lies in Zhang Sheng. His karmic tie of mortal love and the consequent action of paying debts intervene the destiny of Luying. His role in the resurrection of Luying is evident in the film, as he tries to release her soul by chanting sutras. Shortly afterwards, Luying revives in the form of spirit. If looking back to the very first encounter of the lovers, however, we can discover that this is not the fatal moment. The decisive moment can be traced back to the moment Luying once saved Zhang Sheng's life in the wilderness—an intertwining of life and death, an unforeseen stirring of the heart. This act reshapes their fate profoundly.

In the original text, it is Zhang Sheng's mere appreciation of Luying's appearance that drives him to act on her behalf, actively helping to atone for her sins. The film makes a brilliant and innovative adaptation by giving this encounter more ethical weight to the extent that it could be considered an event. The seemingly accidental moment embodies precisely the kind of ontologically significant occurrence Badiou describes. Although their encounter arises amid contingent circumstances, it reveals latent contradictions within the moral and karmic structure of the underworld, opening a space for new possibilities. The encounter, in its ontological significance, thus marks the emergence of something truly new from the impossible (Mo, 2020). From this encounter a seed of difference took root, shattering Luying's fixed course toward immediate reincarnation and bending her destiny onto a new track. In another words, her karmic path was in a sense further unfolded through Zhang Sheng's intervention.

3. Underworld Officials and Their Cinematic Representation

By tracing Zhang Sheng's karmic tie with deity, the ethical universe of the film is further developed accordingly. Why does Meng Po grant Luying to save the vital memories of the vow between she and Zhang Sheng? Earlier in the film, Zhang Sheng and Luying help her push a cart, which might superficially explain her lenience. Yet as an official of the underworld, Meng Po would never violate rules for such a trivial act, and a being of divine power would hardly need help pushing a cart. What matters is not the deed itself but the doers. Meng Po's earlier appearance in non-divine guise

may have been intentional. Compared with the other lifeless souls blindly shuffling forward, only Luying—bound to Zhang Sheng by the karmic tie—and Zhang Sheng himself as a living being retained self-awareness. Thus, this opportunity is less contingent than tailor-made, a sign of recognition of their love. As a moralizing mythological realm, the underworld does not object to rewarding a virtuous couple, thereby creating a story of exemplary love that entails timeless loyalty and devotion, as well as conveying the moral lesson that good deeds are rewarded and reinforcing ethical order for the living.

In Chinese mythology, underworld officials serve not as independent agents but as enforcers of cosmic order, instilling fear among the living. As Ma and Lu (2017) observe, the underworld in traditional beliefs is a bureaucratic system meticulously modeled after earthly governance. The official structure of the underworld directly mirrors the mortal administrative hierarchy, with even similar titles borrowed from imperial bureaucracy. Thus, this deliberate mirroring could enhance the credibility of the afterlife's regulatory mechanisms, as people could easily comprehend and fear a system familiar from their daily lives.

Later, when Zhang Sheng seizes Luying at the brink of reincarnation and flees with her, Meng Po does not intervene. She and her colleges transform into towering statues, gazing down without interference. By then her divine gift of rejuvenation to Zhang Sheng had already taken effect. His karmic bond with the underworld was complete, leaving only the mortal bond of love between two human beings unfinished. To conclude, the innocuous violation of rules by Meng Po, as well as the intentional stand-by, which denotes a finished karmic tie, can exactly be seen as the will of the ethical machinery of the underworld itself as a personified agent. This personified will, impartial yet responsive, continues to orchestrate the moral order, ensuring that acts of virtue and devotion are recognized and that the balance between mortal and divine obligations is meticulously maintained.

How the film represents the underworld officials is intriguing and not surprisingly, coherent with the logic of its ethical universe. In the film, Meng Po and other underworld figures such as Black and White Impermanence are portrayed in ways faithful to this mythological framework. They embody not personal will but the impersonal machinery of the underworld as illustrated. Their karmic bond with Zhang Sheng is exhausted, they merely stand aside as spectators, never intervening directly.

This ethical positioning naturally shapes their visual presence. Their figures recall the solemnity of temple statues, carved or cast at monumental scale to embody the unfathomable power of gods. According to Wang (2020), the Black and White Impermanence Ghosts, long associated with moral judgment and the terrifying notions of death and punishment, is the orthodox image of the underworld. Their iconographies, moreover, are not confined to abstract mythology but are concretely displayed in Cheng Huang (City God) temples for the folks to revere, with their close association with “moral judgement and the terrifying notions of death and punishments”. In folk temples like, such statues are built aloft, their silence signifying their immovability, while the upward gaze of the crowd amplifies their grandeur and distance. The film draws directly on this iconography. The camera frames their towering figures on a low angle, so that viewers share the embodied perspective of worshippers whose awe is mingled with submission. In this way, the representation of underworld officials fuses ritual aesthetics with narrative logic, inheriting and extending the traditional image of deities as inscrutable forces who act not by direct intervention but through the weight of ritualized presence.

4. Comparison with the Turn of Orpheus

The climax of the film centers on Zhang Sheng's daring rescue of Luying from the Huangquan (Yellow Springs). Their reunion after separation ends in failure, mocked by age and coincidence. The reincarnated Luying cannot believe that time has left no trace on Zhang Sheng. She, out of suspicion, deems this young man as an imposter. Despairing, Luying hangs herself, returning once again to the underworld. Only that this time, reincarnation will erase all memory of Zhang Sheng. At this moment, Zhang Sheng dares once more to storm into the Huangquan (Yellow Springs). He

rescues Luying, carries her on his back, and rushes outward without turning back. This very act rekindles her buried, but crucially embodied memories: she recalls how Zhang Sheng once bore her on his back, protecting her with Yang energy so that she as a spirit of the underworld could walk out of the grave to redeem her sins in the living's. Those memories, especially the act of caring her on the back, are deeply embodied, surpassing the misleading veil of appearance.

This image of lovers escaping from the infernal world inevitably evokes the myth of Orpheus, who sought to lead his wife out of Hades, only to doom this rescue at his fatal back glance. Orpheus's turning has given rise to divergent readings. From a psychoanalytic perspective, Hades' command of "no looking back" functions as a prohibition destined to be transgressed, symmetrical with the very structure of desire itself. This paradox is legible that Orpheus is the acting subject and Hades the issuer of the prohibition, namely the big Other to which Orpheus is subjected (Tu & Wang, 2010). Yet as Žižek reminds us, one of the crucial insights of psychoanalysis is that "the law only prohibits what one actually wants to do" (Ma, 2012). The superego, as the obscene reverse side of the law, does not simply prohibit but perversely incites transgression. It commands enjoyment at the very point where symbolic law forbids it. In this sense, Hades' injunction is not a purely symbolic prohibition that guarantees meaning, but a superegoic command saturated with *jouissance*—obscene precisely because it solicits the subject to break it. The prohibition, in other words, is structured to fail since its violation is inscribed into its very form, revealing that desire is sustained by the law's obscene underside.

Another explanation could be resorted to *The Portrait of a Lady on Fire*, where Marianne illustrates that Orpheus at that fatal point chooses to become a poet rather than a lover, so that love is enshrined in memory and eternal mourning instead of confronting the uncertainties of the present (Sciamma, 2019, 01:14:16). Žižek's meditation on art and the Lacanian Thing is instructive here in understanding the poet's mission. Žižek (2004) argues that modern art strives to confront the Real, the unsymbolizable Thing, thereby exposing the violence and limit of representation. As a result, verbal or pictorial "preservation" often amounts to a substitution that kills immediate presence. The poet's attempt to save love by naming or representing it is structurally ambivalent, at once affirming love and betraying it. Orpheus' choice both testifies to love and participates, however invariably, in its deadly symbolic replacement.

In both cases, language, the prohibition that invites desire, or the intuitive of a poet, seduces him into looking back. Ironically, it is also language, the vow between Zhang Sheng and Luying to meet again, that provokes her doubt: is the man she sees truly her beloved from the past life? The promise torments her through the mundanity of waiting and fracture of disappointment, until trust finally collapses. Vows and poetic fantasies are not the whole of love. Beneath them lies embodied devotion within the world.

Zhang Sheng's later predicament, however, diverges sharply from that of Orpheus. Luying's body and endangered life constitute the ultimate prohibition—he must not let go of her. Yet this prohibition is not linguistic but corporeal. It does not summon self-interrogation or symbolic contemplation due to subjection to the big Other. Instead, it presses upon him as sheer material reality. His response, therefore, must not be hesitation but unremitting labor, a ceaseless struggle that leaves no room for reflective pause, for the material reality before him demands his undivided attention to the present.

5. Embodied and Reciprocal Love as Insights for Romantic Relationship

The embodied, ceaseless labor on Zhang Sheng's part exemplifies the very kind of relational engagement Ettinger theorizes, which could be insightful guidelines for romantic relationships. Her theory of the "matrixial" reminds us that subjectivity is not generated in isolation but continually emerges in coexistence with the Other. Drawing on the metaphor of intrauterine cohabitation, she emphasizes that "partial-subjects co-emerge and fade in and out in borderlinking of several I(s) and non-I(s)" (Ettinger, 2006, p. 84, as cited in Fotaki & Harding, 2017).

She also introduces the ethical stance of “self-fragilization,” meaning that one must open space for the Other in order not to cause harm in encounters. In the earlier film, Zhang Sheng’s labor of carrying Luying on his back and protecting her resonates with this framework. As he continues his labor to do virtuous deeds, Luying’s sins are gradually alleviated, thus she transforms from weightless spirit to living flesh, from fragile spirit that could easily vanish to living being. This is the perfect metaphor for the effect of embodied effort. What he performs is an act of “subjectivization through co-affection and response in and by the body,” where love gains ethical thickness through embodied mutual support. His body becomes a site that shelters vulnerability, opening a space where the Other’s fragility can be borne. Both participants are regenerated through embodied interdependence rather than positioned as desiring subject and desired object.

In this sense, the film demonstrates that intimacy is enacted through embodied practice and sustained vulnerability, not through symbolic language. Genuine love then rests on the reciprocal effort for the Other in the materiality of life. It is a devotion realized not by Orpheus, like retrospection, but in ceaseless embodied effort. This embodied reciprocity offers inspiration for modern love. Love is always marked by unexpected encounters, always in need of ceaseless practice and embodied effort. Instead of fretting over metaphysical interrogations, one should uphold a devoted view of love, forever practicing, forever trusting that in the clear conscience lies the strength to resist all doubt.

6. Conclusion

The final chapter of *Curious Tales of a Temple* brings into four interlocking perspectives that together determine its meaning. First, the film draws on folk imagery like karmic debt, resurrection motifs, and the markedly bureaucratic figures of the underworld — to locate the story within a recognizably local ethical universe with both innovative adaptations and visual representation. Second, in behavioral terms the film contrasts directly with the Orpheus myth. Orpheus’s failure is entangled with a retrospective turn (the fatal backward glance), while Zhang Sheng’s stance is immanently practical with sustained labor and physical care. Thus, it gives rise to the film’s insights about love, which are that intimacy is shown as reciprocal, embodied practice, something kept alive by ongoing, mutual responsibility.

References

- Cui, Y., Liu, Y., Xie, J., Zou, J., Huang, H., & Liu, Y. (Directors). (2025, July 12). *Curious tales of a temple* [Film]. Wanda Media Co., Ltd.
- Ding, H., & Zhang, Y. (2023). Paying the “debt of history”: On the ethics of debt responsibility and the reproduction of social memory [in Chinese]. *Thinking*, 49(5), 104–116. <https://doi.org/CNKI:SUN:SXXZ.0.2023-05-012>.
- Ma, L. L. (2017). How institutions are formed: On the role of “underworld judgment” in ancient Chinese social governance [in Chinese]. *New Horizons from Tianfu*, (2), 90–97. <https://doi.org/CNKI:SUN:TFXL.0.2017-02-011>.
- Ma, Y. (2012). The obscene superego: A re-critique of ideology [in Chinese]. *Marxism & Reality*, (2), 128–136. <https://doi.org/10.15894/j.cnki.cn11-3040/a.2012.02.014>
- Mandalaki, E., & Fotaki, M. (2020). The bodies of the commons: Towards a relational embodied ethics of the commons. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 166(4), 745–760. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-020-04581-7>
- Mo, L. (2020). Event and love: Ontological reconstruction of contemporary Western radical left thought [in Chinese]. *Philosophical Study*, (04), 55–61. <https://doi.org/CNKI:SUN:ZXYJ.0.2020-04-007>
- Sciamma, C. (Director & Writer), Merlant, N., & Haenel, A. (Stars). (2019). *Portrait of a Lady on Fire* [Film]. Lilies Films; Arte France Cinéma; Pyramide Films.

Tu, X., & Wang, Y. (2019). From Ovid and Calvino to Lacan: Desire in variations of the Orpheus myth [in Chinese]. *Literary Study*, 5(2), 191–199. <https://doi.org/CNKI:SUN:WPCL.0.2019-02-018>.

Wang, D. K. L. (2020). The Cult of the Underworld in Singapore: Mythology and Materiality. *Religions*, 11(7), 363. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rel11070363>

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